

NetDRIVE Stage One Workshops

Edinburgh and Daresbury

October, 2024

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Cite as: Juckes, M., Sparrow, S., Smith, G., Farmer, J., Jackson, A., Cornish, G., Bane, M., Udayakumar, A., Geatches, D., and Ramsden, L. (2025). NetDRIVE Stage One Workshops at Edinburgh and Daresbury. Zenodo. [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14778528](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778528)

Overview

The Network for sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise (NetDRIVE) has been set up to provide a forum for managers, software engineers, academics, and others to come together to build a common vision for a sustainable future and to incite a transition to sustainable working practices in the Digital Research Infrastructure communities

NetDRIVE brings together creative thinking from across UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) to enable change through technological progress, to build a common vision of a sustainable future, and to incite a transition to sustainable working practices in the DRI communities. The project aims to provide leadership in the UK and globally, exploiting the strength-in depth of a centuries long tradition of academic institutions driving change for societal benefit.

The NetDRIVE ambition is to:

- A. Provide timely and actionable advice to inform UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Investment decisions.
- B. Provide UKRI and their community with confidence for delivery of the roadmap for achieving carbon neutrality in their DRI by 2040 or sooner.
- C. Enable UKRI to play a positive and leading role in the national and global transition to a sustainable economy.

The project is now in Stage 1, which is focused on building the Stage 2 proposal. Stage 2, if funded, will run from 9 January 2025 to 31 March 2028, with a full economic cost (FEC) of up to £3.96 million. This will fund a network of experts, four champions and a portfolio of community activities and projects.

In stage one - running from July to December 2024 - two co-coordinators, Martin Juckes and Sarah Sparrow, have been funded to produce a proposal for stage two which will be a 39-month project starting January 9th, 2025, with a budget ceiling of £3.96m (100% FEC).

Community feedback on key elements of the proposal concept and approach were gathered through two workshops held on 9th and 10th October in Edinburgh and 21st and 22nd of October in Daresbury. Meetings combined a selection of invited speakers to

stimulate discussion, presentation on NetDRIVE plans from Sarah and Martin, breakout discussions to permit in-depth discussion by delegates, and plenary sessions.

Workshop Questions (as presented to the workshop attendees)

During the workshop, there will be breakout groups for discussion of key aspects of the project. We would like delegates to focus on four questions:

1. Given the remit set out in the 2nd paragraph above, what would you consider as the key priorities for NetDRIVE work from now to March 2028?
2. How do we frame the roles of the champions to attract, motivate and empower the right people for this challenge?
3. How do we make the Network of Experts accessible and effective?
4. Where are the easy wins and the barriers that we need to prioritise?

Questions 2 and 3 will be supported by documents with draft role descriptions for the champions and a draft term of reference for project activities.

Workshop agendas are given in Appendix 1. Delegates are listed in Appendix 2 and links presentations made in the meetings are in Appendix 3.

Key elements of the recommendations have been incorporated into the proposed workplan for Stage Two (submitted November 21st, 2024):

1. Rather than four champions recruited into the core team there will be 8 to 10 champion awards, each working at around 20% FTE. This will enable greater diversity in the champion team and avoid concerns about potentially substantial difficulties recruiting suitable people to a novel and time-limited role.
2. In addition to funding community projects, the flexible fund will be used to fund Working Groups, Task Forces, and Focus Meetings in order to maintain a high level of community engagement and interaction.
3. Support for early-career champions and network members is built into the budget and workplan. Initial plans committed to being accessible to early career participation but did not make explicit plans to provide support to foster constructive engagement.
4. A list of activities which should be funded early in the project:
 - Four Community Projects:
 - CP1.1 Training/summer school for DRI users: exploiting existing knowledge at key centres to fill a gap in training.

- CP1.2 Energy savings through tuning hardware configuration: following up on a key success in the scoping project
 - CP1.3 Guide to best practice and existing tools: exploiting community knowledge.
 - CP1.4 Status snapshot on community readiness: providing a foundation for tracking progress.
 - Two Working Groups:
 - Working Group on Ethics and Sustainable Progress to Net Zero (WGESP)
 - Working Group on Monitoring and Reporting (WGMAR)
 - And one Focus Meeting
 - London, February 2025, to provide initial guidance for large investments
5. After the advice to remove the champions from the core team (point 1. above), there was also advice to keep the core team strong, and to ensure a strong social science element. This has been addressed by introducing a full-time Integration Lead in the core team, with responsibility for developing teamwork and monitoring trust and confidence.

A full list of recommendations is listed in the next section.

There was also positive feedback about the format of the meetings and support for further meetings following the same general format.

Workshop Comments and Recommendations

Comments and recommendations were initially organised under four topics: key priorities, champion roles, the network, and quick wins. After early feedback questioning the wisdom of concentrating on quick wins and potentially delaying action on major challenges the last of these was changed to a discussion of recommendations on three planning horizons: (1) what we are doing now, (2) what we plan to do, and (3) opportunities and risks beyond our current plans.

Key Priorities

1. Trust: providing a trusted and accessible source of information, tools, and data
2. Progress: demonstrate tangible emissions reductions
3. Standards: Green labs certification, reporting rules, clearly defined and mandated metadata, clarity about meaning of "net zero"; Better understanding of what is really being reported in PUE figures; Create a shared dictionary

4. Community: review and share best practice, foster grass roots activities
5. It is important to support deployment/implementation of what is already near-readiness and support existing community-led efforts
6. Vision: clear vision for a UKRI DRI (as opposed to market approach); clarity about what NetDRIVE will do
7. Competitive: environmental sustainability should not damage research infrastructure competitiveness
8. Embed: bring sustainability into funding and ethical considerations
9. Enable: empower and enable progress through incremental steps and learning by doing
10. Gaps: identify and address gaps
11. HPC Investments: need for an early steer
12. Carbon budget: understanding the split between HPC and other DRI elements; mandate accounting of power and carbon; Encourage reporting by setting a cautious (high carbon) default;
13. Clarity around embedded carbon is crucial. Estimates made at the COSMA HPC facility in Durham suggest that, for a typical 5-year operational system, 66% of the carbon footprint is in the manufacturing supply chain.
14. When embedded carbon is accounted for Solid State Drives (SSD) are highly likely to have a higher carbon footprint than Hard Disk Drive (HDD)
15. Waste heat: understanding where we can take advantage of it
16. People: should we invest more in people and skills
17. Take compute to the power: e.g. offshore wind
18. Understanding the CPU/GPU balance; do we need up-skilling
19. Embed Green Software Engineering
20. Fund longer projects (including software are projects) as in France (5-10 years)
21. Incentives: Remove incentives to burn allocation at end of year; reward good coding (c.f. lower insurance for advanced drivers)
22. Link to external tools -- e.g. Octopus API on green electricity
23. Respect and understand diversity of data centres
24. Map stakeholders and landscape of existing projects and activities
25. Motivate leaders and others to take actions
26. Treated a bit more like health and safety - so it is fundamental and needs to be done
27. Get comms message out about NetDRIVE first so people know when trying to commute

28. There is a clear need for NetDrive to make solid recommendations before future large procurement processes start over the next couple of years (including Archer, DiRAC, Tier-2)
29. Clear communication between funders and community is needed to coordinate actions

Champion Roles

1. Recruit more people at lower FTE to enhance diversity and give more focus to each role. Look into secondments or champions attached to an institute (for greater uptake).
2. Provide clarity about what success will be for a champion and avoid excessive responsibilities and requirements.
3. Empower early career champions through support, training, mentorship. Exploit SSI ambassador framework.
4. Define interface to co-coordinators more clearly: champions should be engaged in strategic thinking, not leg work.
5. Give them a role overseeing community projects.
6. Social aspect should be integrated in all champion roles.
7. Risk of losing focus if spread across many people
8. Champions must have networking skills; need to be passionate about the role; must define effective role in application.
9. Risk that early career champions will lack authority
10. Need to plan for sustainable impact
11. Institutions need to understand what their benefit is from allocating staff to projects. Champions should have explicit recognition from host institutions.
12. Somebody needs to be in charge of pulling together effort and outputs from the champions.
13. There are funding gaps: dept energy and net zero does not fund net zero research.
14. Need to report on benefits — demonstrate a cost benefit
15. Engagement with civil servants is positive and beneficial — longer term perspective than Government.
16. We need more reported information, even if absolute value is unclear, it will have a relative value.
17. Early career champions and experts will need advice.
18. Value of community activity needs to be visible;
19. Champions should have explicit recognition from host institutions.
20. Need information on scope of possible savings.

21. Should involve industry sector bodies, e.g. techUK
22. Will need to follow the Chatham house rule when industry present
23. Need a plan do deal with exaggerated net zero claims by others.
24. Need to engage with small cloud providers

NetWORK

1. More clarity about expert role and size of network; clear incentives for taking part
2. Emphasise importance of plain language; building trust
3. Recruit people with track records of being accessible community representatives
4. Leverage existing networks (e.g. HDR UK, SSI, research consortia, University Sustainability committees)
5. Clarity about chairing and structures within network and working group structures (learn from RDA and DARE UK): Structure reports (cf IPCC) to separate technical and policy guidance.
6. Comms strategy for key events for diverse groups; community feedback and suggestion mechanism; briefing notes; mailing list; Create a forum space (c.f. <https://forum.esce-community.org>) need robust existing platform, public facing and private options
7. Network self-correcting (e.g. following the Social Media Council¹ concept). Controlled in and out point of the network of opinions in response to a question. Ok to say, “opinions divided”. Would be useful to have a role to help interpret things. Helping people understand supplier claims etc.
8. Controlling who is part of the network to be authoritative. Trust can be earned through good quality reports that are generated. Reports are part of the aspect for gaining authority.
9. Constant visibility is required to kept in peoples mind for authoritative part.
10. Experts expected to contribute their own time. Some costs available for travel etc. for expert meetings
11. Measure of effectiveness need to be determined. The carbon footprint of the network needs to be transparent
12. Working groups to focus on different areas (can be cross-theme) - network members can sit in multiple

¹ <https://www.article19.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/A19-SMC.pdf>

13. Open call for recruitment - process for vetting to be decided, panel required - could these be made up of champions (though they are unlikely to be in place for the first network call)?
14. 100-200 experts, working groups 10-20 with workshops on themes. Structure needed to govern to ensure communication between working groups. SSI fellows more like 20-30, unfunded - 200 would be too many.
15. 2 years membership in network with option to renew - people may not want to commit long term.
16. Training for the group of experts? How to be affective part of a network?

Easy Wins (==> Three Horizons)

1. Balancing urgency versus importance: Should make sure difficult issues are not neglected. Reframe around "3 horizons": what we are doing, what is planned, what could happen. Look at things that have a long lead time as well as high immediate impact; Encourage easy small step; case studies
2. Sharing: share information, including information on challenges, existing tools. Enabling knowledge transfer: Set up a knowledge base, with contributions from network. Clarity in language; clear communication strategy
3. Explore potential to reduce power consumption through hardware configuration management,
4. Initial community project on training
5. Exploit existing activities (e.g. STFC summer schools; Green Software Foundation course; Energy Efficient High Performance Working Group (International Group)); Look at international best practise. Learn from existing sustainability plans - get experts to bring knowledge and best practice from these existing frameworks
6. STFC have summer schools - have session in that.
7. Ambiguity about authority is a barrier,
8. Invite senior members of organisations to London meeting to get buy in
9. We should practice what we preach - organise meetings accessible by rail in Europe, global engagement online
10. Management needs to be on board - how can we empower people to have these conversations
11. Communication needs to be effective to get buy in from higher levels
12. Recommendations need to be actioned - all levels need to feel engaged to implement changes. Peer learning is way to make a difference
13. Education of early carer staff

14. Consider publishing experiment plans and share outcomes to avoid duplicating work which otherwise is not discoverable/known about until a paper is published.
15. Training to induce behaviour change/inspire new thinking - embed in mandatory online modules - but also offer alternative access/dissemination routes for different communities
16. Unclear how much efficiency reduction is acceptable if zero is the true aim.
17. Challenging to differentiate between bad practice and user error.
18. Barrier: Services can be difficult to engage with and can dis-incentivise users.
19. Barrier: Changing perspective that facilities do not cost (money and energy!) as users are removed from the process without individual billing - make costs more apparent at the point of individual use.

Appendix 1: Workshop Agendas

Edinburgh

Day 1 October 9th 13:00-17:00	
13:00	Lunch and arrival
13:30	Welcome and overview – Martin and Sarah
14:00	Keynote 1: Lorna Smith, Machine Rooms and Hardware
14:30	Machine Rooms and Hardware Discussion
15:00	Break out group session 1: Q1 & Q2
15:25	Break out summary
15:30	Coffee Break
15:45	Gordon Shaw Blair: Systematic Change
16:15	Systematic Change Discussion
16:40	Break out group session 2: Q3 & Q4
16:55	Break out summary
17:00	Finish

Day 2 October 10th 09:00-13:00	
09:00	Coffee and arrival
09:30	Day 2 welcome and reflection on day 1 – Martin and Sarah
09:45	Keynote 2: Michele Weiland: Green Software Engineering
10:15	Green Software Engineering Discussion
10:30	Break out group session 3: Revisit all questions
10:45	Coffee break
11:00	Break out summary
11:05	Panel on Galvanising Individual Action
11:30	Discussion on missing items
12:00	Lunch and summary
13:00	Finish

Daresbury

Day 1 October 21st 12:00-17:00	
12:00	Registration and buffet lunch
12:45	Welcome and overview – Martin and Sarah
13:15	Keynote 1: Christin Merritt, Skills, and Career Pathways
13:45	Keynote 2: Loïc Lannelongue
14:15	Plenary discussion
14:45	Refreshment Break
15:00	Breakout discussions: Q1 & Q2

16:00	Feedback from breakouts with whole group summary
16:45	Group discussion – London project launch
17:25	Reminder of tomorrow’s workshop
17:30	Close

Day 2 October 22nd 08:30-12:30	
08:30	Tea/Coffee and arrival
08:55	Day 2 welcome and reflection on day 1 – Martin and Sarah
09:00	Keynote 3: Michael Rudgyard
09:30	Keynote 4: Tom Griffin
10:00	Plenary discussion
10:30	Refreshment break
10:45	Breakout discussions: Q3 & Q4
11:45	Feedback from breakouts, discussion, and consolidation
12:25	Next steps and close
12:30	Buffet lunch
13:30	Close

Appendix 2: Workshop Attendees

NetDRIVE Event - University of Edinburgh (In Person)

Andy Turner
 Ioana Colfescu
 Caroline Lord

Kristy Pringle
Alastair Basden
Anjali Bhatt
Adrian Jackson
Kieran Leach
Andrew Wood
Jaana Pinnick
Martin Juckes
James Richings
Sarah Sparrow
Dr Alex owen
Aparna Udayakumar
Francisco Duran del Fierro
Cian O'Donovan
Lorna Smith
Michele Weiland
Sean McGeever
Lisa Otty
Louise Chisholm

NetDRIVE Event - University of Edinburgh (Online)

Loïc Lannelongue
Alison Packer
Wei Wang
Danilo Bueno
Ritchie Somerville
Justin O'Byrne

NetDRIVE Event - Daresbury Laboratory (In Person)

Cristin Merritt
Dan Walker
Dave Cable
David McDonagh
Gemma Cornsiah
Harry Swift

Ilian Todorov
James Groves
Jessica Huntley
Loïc Lannelongue
Mark Wilkinson
Martin Juckes
Michael Bane
Michael Rudgyard
Robert Jennings
Sam Tygier
Sarah Campbell
Sarah Sidders
Sarah Sparrow
Shaun de Witt
Tao- Tao Chang
Thomas Gardner
Tom Griffin

NetDRIVE Event - Daresbury Laboratory (Online)

Bryan Lawrence
Chaminuka Mbanje
Elliott Kasaor
Evgeniia Vdovichenko
Fatima Chami
James Earl-Fraser
Neil Massey
Patrick Austin
Wim Vanderbauwhede
Laura McGuire
Adrian Jackson
Dawn Geatches

Appendix 3: Presentations

Presentation Slides from the Edinburgh workshop:

- [NetDRIVE Overview Presentation](#)
- [Green Software Engineering](#). Michèle Weiland

- [Sustainability at the Advance Computing Facility \(ACF\)](#) Paul Clark, Adrian Jackson, Alan Simpson, Lorna Smith, Ritchie Somerville, Andy Turner EPCC, University of Edinburgh

Presentation slides from the Daresbury workshop:

- [Systematic Change for Sustainable Computing](#), Michael Rudgyard
- [Move the needle- Skills and Career Pathways](#), Cristin Merritt, Alces Flight